

Supplementary Materials

Gene-associated Methylation of *ST14* is associated with survival and hormone receptor positivity in breast cancer

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Table S1: Genes with non-zero coefficients were identified

Genes	Coefficients
ACTA2	-0.2459142
APC	0.1909728
AXL	0.6351006
IGFBP7	0.2928156
MMP14	0.2237096
PLAU	-0.1156647
PLAUR	-0.3063885
SNAI1	-0.1431026
SNAI2	-0.3452794
SPINT2	-0.3276541
XBP1	0.5041034
ZEB2	-0.630038

Table S2: DMPs for TCGA between high and low GAM statuses

DMPs for TCGA between high and low GAM statuses						
ID	Feature	cgi	logFC	A.Expression	P value	A.P value
cg01497747	Body	island	0.16071448	0.7099234	5.04E-59	1.71E-57
cg22110158	Body	opensea	0.1373584	0.5645659	9.82E-36	3.34E-35
cg02850715	TSS1500	shore	0.11914509	0.6826242	1.01E-36	4.29E-36
cg10356767	Body	island	0.10932944	0.851361	4.60E-37	2.23E-36
cg25034478	Body	island	0.08224832	0.918314	2.19E-28	5.72E-28
cg09712902	Body	opensea	0.07462648	0.8171128	5.40E-49	6.11E-48
cg23250795	Body	shore	0.0730131	0.902649	4.70E-29	1.45E-28
cg09174502	Body	island	0.0663757	0.9409666	1.04E-19	1.86E-19
cg10159728	Body	shore	0.0622474	0.8892255	5.50E-27	1.33E-26
cg15863552	Body	island	0.05802842	0.9275459	7.66E-29	2.17E-28
cg04823219	Body	island	0.05381069	0.8656176	5.67E-25	1.29E-24
cg14830082	Body	opensea	0.05062074	0.854681	3.39E-23	7.20E-23
cg02637309	Body	shelf	0.04403145	0.8507018	4.68E-49	6.11E-48
cg13689118	3'UTR	shore	0.04266069	0.9020713	7.87E-36	2.97E-35
cg03098782	Body	opensea	0.04248593	0.9094799	1.19E-18	2.03E-18
cg05284912	Body	opensea	0.04112167	0.8980987	4.45E-43	3.78E-42
cg06443648	Body	shore	0.03314992	0.9111251	8.65E-43	5.88E-42
cg25892168	Body	island	0.03284515	0.8943559	1.06E-21	2.12E-21
cg07606115	Body	opensea	0.03062927	0.9112812	1.61E-37	9.12E-37
cg15298666	Body	island	0.029855292	0.9677756	4.47E-14	6.90E-14
cg02643834	Body	shore	0.02358449	0.8566922	8.77E-20	1.66E-19
cg11069338	Body	shore	0.013979	0.9739816	1.36E-05	1.92E-05
cg24991874	Body	opensea	0.010732657	0.9062986	3.26E-06	4.82E-06
cg22817719	Body	opensea	0.009383375	0.9573083	3.93E-05	5.35E-05
cg11951433	Body	island	0.003265977	0.9769777	2.67E-04	3.49E-04
cg11035519	Body	opensea	-0.068819996	0.3576351	1.69E-15	2.73E-15

Table S3: DMPs for GSE75067 between high and low GAM statuses

DMPs for GSE75067 between high and low GAM statuses						
ID	feature	cgi	logFC	AveExpr	P.Value	adj.P.Val
cg01497747	Body	island	0.234566441	0.75404583	3.93E-21	1.34E-19
cg25034478	Body	island	0.124083538	0.92333668	8.58E-17	1.46E-15
cg10356767	Body	island	0.113941029	0.82626521	7.44E-09	6.33E-08
cg22110158	Body	opensea	0.105401562	0.59997374	5.93E-05	1.68E-04
cg02850715	TSS1500	shore	0.099051962	0.71708775	9.99E-05	2.61E-04
cg09174502	Body	island	0.093120089	0.94929855	3.61E-08	2.46E-07
cg23250795	Body	shore	0.086467745	0.878395	7.73E-10	8.76E-09
cg09712902	Body	opensea	0.070335533	0.90376549	1.81E-06	7.71E-06
cg04823219	Body	island	0.057925056	0.93890406	2.73E-05	1.03E-04
cg15863552	Body	island	0.055830907	0.90362965	4.84E-07	2.35E-06
cg03098782	Body	opensea	0.05252912	0.8932968	4.24E-05	1.44E-04
cg14830082	Body	opensea	0.045120682	0.83838074	3.46E-04	6.92E-04
cg10159728	Body	shore	0.03404117	0.8513582	1.11E-02	1.71E-02
cg02643834	Body	shore	0.030323522	0.87573956	5.01E-05	1.55E-04
cg15298666	Body	island	0.028689244	0.98763028	2.37E-07	1.34E-06
cg02637309	Body	shelf	0.026534786	0.94340894	5.38E-04	1.02E-03
cg11069338	Body	shore	0.025110823	0.98826963	3.43E-03	6.14E-03
cg25892168	Body	island	0.024256279	0.975341	2.25E-04	4.79E-04
cg13689118	3'UTR	shore	0.022738279	0.98748334	1.51E-04	3.66E-04
cg07606115	Body	opensea	0.021692578	0.98330078	9.39E-03	1.52E-02
cg05284912	Body	opensea	0.019155772	0.97754255	1.67E-04	3.78E-04
cg06443648	Body	shore	0.013702368	0.99345467	5.13E-03	8.72E-03
cg18373354	1stExon	island	0.007481755	0.01499882	2.41E-02	3.57E-02

Table S4: Differential gene expression analysis for TCGA cohort

Differential gene expression analysis for TCGA cohort							
Gene	baseMean	log2FoldChange	lfcSE	stat	pvalue	padj	(-log10P)
XBP1	41928.36131	1.127342455	0.090818234	12.41317307	2.22E-35	5.99E-34	33.22257318
CDKL2	20.02116508	0.751774938	0.158728101	4.736243518	2.18E-06	5.88E-06	5.230622674
CDH1	10485.46147	0.340702985	0.104661137	3.255296024	0.001132742	0.002038936	2.690596406
ERN1	201.8898464	0.334388703	0.097669658	3.42367026	0.000617815	0.001191501	2.923905589
NCOA4	4774.06822	0.278002108	0.049502153	5.615959964	1.95E-08	5.86E-08	7.232102384
ZEB1	663.2669361	0.241672027	0.057193144	4.22554188	2.38E-05	5.36E-05	4.27083521
SNIP1	348.0100822	0.133685686	0.041562616	3.216488725	0.001297696	0.002189863	2.659583054
ZEB2	631.8499083	-0.200647695	0.053286555	-3.765446924	0.000166251	0.000345291	3.461814741
DDR2	202.8269796	-0.284733597	0.08934469	-3.186911251	0.001438009	0.002283897	2.641323486
CDCP1	1209.608051	-0.362252014	0.077795391	-4.656471393	3.22E-06	7.90E-06	5.102372909
ACTA2	7335.793374	-0.406646578	0.071925167	-5.653745376	1.57E-08	5.30E-08	7.27572413
CLDN2	8.86301614	-0.476901821	0.150919781	-3.159968946	0.00157786	0.002366789	2.625840458
PLAU	1838.222489	-0.482077999	0.079112574	-6.093569867	1.10E-09	4.26E-09	8.370590401
VIM	22491.27046	-0.542427773	0.059130711	-9.173368025	4.58E-20	3.09E-19	18.51004152
SNAI2	475.3498788	-0.65709006	0.076044872	-8.640820075	5.58E-18	2.51E-17	16.60032628
SNAI1	139.5635494	-0.742037235	0.077667542	-9.554019758	1.25E-21	1.12E-20	19.95078198
PLAUR	813.8520801	-0.746746739	0.074801774	-9.983008473	1.81E-23	2.44E-22	21.61261017
FOXC2	22.58729813	-1.152803199	0.132834162	-8.678514465	4.01E-18	2.17E-17	16.66354027

Table S5: Differential gene expression analysis for GSE5364

Differential gene expression analysis for GSE5364							
Gene	baseMean	log2FoldChange	lfcSE	stat	pvalue	padj	(-log10P)
XBP1	5096.928091	1.664140211	0.095724453	17.38469284	1.08E-67	4.42E-66	65.35474599
RGS16	611.8690452	0.383834672	0.097809675	3.924301679	8.70E-05	0.000356625	3.44778835
CDH1	1262.125848	0.334758978	0.108660751	3.080771794	0.002064648	0.00604647	2.218498111
AKT1	1207.71962	0.216933259	0.084188239	2.576764408	0.00997299	0.024052505	1.618839689
IGFBP7	4828.337322	0.180162203	0.072866088	2.472510987	0.013416759	0.030560395	1.514841031
TGFB1	98.16497326	-0.176406517	0.059216999	-2.978984396	0.002892055	0.00790495	2.102100846
CDKN2C	174.9793983	-0.229834414	0.085520437	-2.687479428	0.007199354	0.018448344	1.734042616
CD44	935.1217399	-0.260838126	0.080257653	-3.250009376	0.001154012	0.00374979	2.425993064
PLAUR	428.2506216	-0.323005836	0.080827642	-3.996229849	6.44E-05	0.000293192	3.532847685
SPINT1	1051.090509	-0.337228433	0.104034173	-3.241515957	0.001188958	0.00374979	2.425993064
RAD51	67.98713289	-0.342261237	0.093692327	-3.653033785	0.00025916	0.00096596	3.015040661
PLAU	814.062884	-0.460142795	0.097931605	-4.698613816	2.62E-06	1.34E-05	4.872115572
MMP14	186.3469035	-0.517649019	0.095118509	-5.442148155	5.26E-08	3.08E-07	6.510982921
CDCP1	469.8735971	-0.530346087	0.084513343	-6.275294169	3.49E-10	2.38E-09	8.622574493
DDR2	374.5095352	-0.62882414	0.087966662	-7.148437002	8.78E-13	1.20E-11	10.92098381
ACTA2	5628.596265	-0.675083046	0.097519461	-6.922546952	4.44E-12	3.64E-11	10.4391998
ACTA2.1	5629.112163	-0.675083048	0.097519438	-6.922548575	4.44E-12	3.64E-11	10.4391998
SNAI2	560.296286	-0.806455588	0.106444786	-7.576280832	3.56E-14	7.29E-13	12.13728239

Table S6: Differential gene expression analysis for GSE22820

Differential gene expression analysis for GSE22820							
Gene	baseMean	log2FoldChange	lfcSE	stat	pvalue	padj	(-log10P)
XBP1	1137.795879	1.000388315	0.123028617	8.131346482	4.25E-16	1.74E-14	13.7592894
PLAUR	1320.48609	-0.85633365	0.133332315	-6.42255143	1.34E-10	2.75E-09	8.561112351
ACTA2	1276.089657	-0.792820317	0.132781339	-5.97087152	2.36E-09	3.23E-08	7.491444666
SNAI1	1257.48492	-0.656263744	0.120745703	-5.43508986	5.48E-08	5.61E-07	6.250742729
DDR2	1161.521909	-0.560715607	0.107584439	-5.21186533	1.87E-07	1.53E-06	5.814457793
SNAI2	1173.658981	-0.598221667	0.119472771	-5.00717996	5.52E-07	3.77E-06	5.423166544
ZEB2	1131.766889	-0.466100201	0.097568727	-4.77714748	1.78E-06	1.04E-05	4.982383963
CD44	2619.397705	-0.467982307	0.105705116	-4.42724368	9.54E-06	4.89E-05	4.310553473
NCOA4	1142.249788	0.368796431	0.09395882	3.925085816	8.67E-05	0.000394961	3.403445443
CDKN2C	3598.669321	-0.61857544	0.162883799	-3.79764865	0.000146075	0.000598908	3.222639723
VIM	1115.673493	-0.287383855	0.078066208	-3.68128363	0.000232063	0.000864961	3.063003537
PLAU	1329.695496	-0.465052293	0.131564843	-3.53477633	0.00040812	0.001394412	2.855609031
PRSS8	2583.965218	0.34522168	0.110600644	3.121335176	0.00180033	0.005677964	2.245807384
NOTCH2	2607.396473	0.306401167	0.102118946	3.000434096	0.002695951	0.007895285	2.102632205
CDH1	1274.225019	0.398191613	0.140881686	2.826425656	0.004707067	0.012865983	1.890557031
APC	1117.341305	0.254560606	0.095430076	2.667509202	0.00764158	0.019581548	1.708152982
STK11	2473.600401	0.21207951	0.08155923	2.600312814	0.009313882	0.022462891	1.648534351
RAD51	3453.679099	-0.438323854	0.173190207	-2.53088128	0.011377635	0.025915724	1.586436654
TGFB1	2410.110641	0.230764816	0.093955864	2.456098054	0.014045483	0.030308673	1.518433073
AKT1	2608.70353	0.261287672	0.108840703	2.400643008	0.016366294	0.033550903	1.474295782
CDCP1	1204.817677	-0.293493075	0.130367437	-2.25127594	0.024368066	0.045413213	1.342817769
TP53	2799.007138	-0.276037129	0.122373664	-2.25569064	0.024090012	0.045413213	1.342817769

Table S7: Correlation between cg11035519 methylation and gene expression

Correlation between cg11035519 methylation and gene expression	
Gene_name	Pearson's correlation
FOXC1	0.654852299823652
FAM171A1	0.65091368836128
RGMA	0.636750952971253
SFRP1	0.62234591612747
CHST3	0.610455101388426
PTX3	0.607771089823358

Figure S1. Study flowchart

Figure. 2 Progression-free survival in BRCA cohort

Figure S3 Snapshot of CpG beta value distribution between normal and tumor samples from Xena browser

Figure S4 DMPs between normal and tumor tissues in TCGA cohort

Figure S5. Snapshot of the percentage of hormone status for TCGA primary tumor cohort from Xena browser

